

Classification and Analysis of Mental State using EEG Signals

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Abstract-- Electroencephalogram (EEG) signals reflect the gross electrical activity produced from synaptic current of individual neurons across large cortical area. EEG signals are used in study and analysis of neurons i.e. to study and analysis of the brain/mental State. Analysis and study of neurons show major evolution in research related to medical and biomedical World. With the help of EEG signals obtain from neurons many unknown facts and information get uncovered and this facts and information playing an important role in research such as for evaluation of various neurological disorder & implementation of Brain Computer Interface (BCI). In this work, we are doing analysis and classification of EEG signals for knowing the mental state after and before consumption of caffeine. As it is known scientifically as well as we can also feel the potent of caffeine after consumption. Here we are going to do a comparative study of EEG signals, recorded during caffeine consumption state and controlled state for same mental task. For classifying and analysis of EEG signals, recorded in both the situations Wavelet transformation used.

Keywords-- Brain computer interface; Independent component analysis; Artifact; support vector machine (SVM) and Artificial neural networks (ANN).

I. INTRODUCTION

The study of human complex body structure has been going on since hundreds of years, to know and understand this complex structure. One of the most complicated part of this complex structure is HUMAN BRAIN. Human brain is work as central processing system of human body, Brain made up of billions of neurons.

Every neuron is made of a cell body, dendrites and an axon. Dendrites and axons are nerve fibers. There are about 86 billion neurons in the human brain, which comprises roughly 10% of all brain cells.

For every cerebral activity, neurons produce electric signals. They can be regarded as output of a system. Mental states and emotions can be considered as state variables of system [2]. This electric signals are removed and quantitatively measured with process of sensing technology. This helps to improve research related to different mental state and emotions. A change in the mental state of a person is often reflect as a change in electric signals produced by neurons [2].

Such signals generally deliver in indirect way information about physiological functions, which are related to the brain. Possible applications using such signals are very numerous. They are for example integrated in the design of new technological devices with embedded intelligence and allow for Brain-Computer-Interfaces. There is also an important demand, in the medical domain, for automatic signal interpretation systems [2]. BCI is composed of signal collection and processing, pattern identification and control systems [3].

In our study, EEG data sets are collected by a system. From the EEG datasets obtained Delta, Theta, and Alpha & Beta waves are extracted by using wavelet transform.

II. MATERIAL

A. EEG Signals

However, although some devices such as magnetic resonance (MR), brain tomography (BT) are used to diagnose the structural disorders of brain, for observing some special illnesses especially such as epilepsy. The electrical activity of active nerve cells in the brain produces currents spreading through the head. [4] These currents also reach the scalp surface, and resulting voltage differences on the scalp can be recorded as the electroencephalogram (EEG) by electrodes on or inside the brain with 10-20 electrode placement system. This 10 - 20 lead system provides information of how the brain functions over time. [6] Most commonly it is used to show the type and location of the activity in the brain during a seizure. It also is used to evaluate people who are having problems associated with brain function. These problems might include confusion, coma, and tumors, with long-term difficulties with thinking or memory, or weakening of specific parts of the body. EEG is a recording of the brain's electrical activity, made from the scalp. There are five major brain waves distinguished by their different frequency ranges. These frequency bands are: delta (δ) (3Hz and below), theta (θ) (3.5Hz-7.5Hz), alpha(α) (7.5-13Hz), beta(β) (14Hz and greater) and Gamma (γ) (31 - 100 Hz) waveforms. [12]

B. 10-20 System

The "10-20" system is an internationally recognized method which describes the location of scalp electrodes for an EEG test, as shown in Fig.1. This system is based on the relationship between the location of an electrode and the underlying area of cerebral cortex. The numeric term "10" and "20" means the distances between adjacent electrodes are either 10% or 20% of the total front - back or right - left distance of the skull. Each site has a letter to identify the lobe and a number to identify the hemisphere location. The letters F, T, C, P and O stand for frontal, temporal, central, parietal and occipital respectively and number, odd no. lie in the left & even no. lie in the right side of the hemisphere.

Figure 1

C. Frequency Band of EEG Signal

The brain waves recorded from the scalp have small amplitude of approximately $100\mu\text{V}$. The frequencies of these brain waves range from 0.5 to 100 Hz, and their characteristics are highly dependent on the degree of activity of the cerebral cortex. Generally, in normal persons, the brain waves may be classified as belonging to one of four wave group.

1. Delta (δ) -The Delta waves which include all the waves in the EEG below 3.5 Hz. They occur in deep sleep, in childhood, and in serious organic brain disease.
2. Theta (θ) -The Theta waves have frequencies between 4 and 7 Hz. These occur mainly during the childhood, but they also occur during emotional stress in some adults.
3. Alpha (α) -The Alpha waves are rhythmic waves occurring at a frequency range between 8 and 13 Hz, which are found in all normal persons when they are awake in a quiet, resting state of cerebration.
4. Beta (β) - The Beta waves are very low amplitude, and high frequency range between 13 and 30 Hz. They are affected by mental activity. [6]

III. METHODOLOGY

Figure 2: Block Diagram of Methodology

In this study, first EEG waveforms have been used in Ref.13. One of the EEG waveform as shown above. Then, the wavelet transforms of the EEG waveforms are taken by using daubechies wavelets. The decomposition of the signal leads to a set of coefficients called wavelet coefficients. Therefore the signal can be constructed as a linear combination of the wavelet functions weighted by the wavelet coefficients. In this paper 6 level decomposition is done. Therefore, ψ_1 (1-3 Hz), ψ_2 (4-8 Hz), ψ_3 (9-13 Hz), and ψ_4 (14-30 Hz) wavelets of the original EEG waveform are obtained. The ψ_1 , ψ_2 , ψ_3 , and ψ_4 waves are viewed in the Fig.2. Since the EEG signals do not have any useful frequency components above 30 Hz, Thus, the EEG signals were decomposed into details D1–D6 and one final Approximation, A6. An approximate coefficient of 6th level decomposition is a signal with frequency range 1 to 3 Hz. Approximation coefficients of 6th level are reconstructed and a signal is obtained.

A. Subjects

Subjects Ten healthy male subjects aged 22–33 years (mean B SD 25 B 4 years), weighing between 59 and 84 kg (71 B 8 kg) and 171–184 cm (179 B 5 cm) in height were enrolled in the study. The study was conducted according to the Declaration of Helsinki (Summerset West Amendment 1996). Written informed consent from the subjects and approval from the Hospital Ethics Committee (Dresden, Germany) were obtained. The subjects were moderate users of caffeine. This means they consumed 1–2 cups of coffee per day.

B. Protocol

The subjects were not allowed to smoke or to consume alcoholic or caffeine-containing beverages for 10 h before and during the trial. They had to have been free of medication for at least 14 days. After an overnight fast, the subjects presented themselves in the morning. They received 200 mg of caffeine

orally as powder with 150 ml of water solution as well as placebo (glucose) on two different occasions under randomized, double-blind, crossover conditions. All recordings took place in a quiet room with the subjects sitting in a comfortable chair. Quantitative EEG was recorded before and 30 min after ingestion of caffeine and placebo with the subjects keeping their eyes open and closed for periods of 15 min each. Heart rate was monitored by hand at the end of each period.

IV. ARTIFACT REJECTION

Artifact rejection plays a key role in many signal processing applications. The artifacts are disturbance that can occur during the signal acquisition and that can alter the analysis of the signals themselves. Our aim is to automatically remove the artifacts, in particular from the EEG recordings. The artifact rejection is based on the independent component analysis (ICA).

Five different methods used for detecting trials containing artifacts.

1) Extreme values: First, we used standard thresholding of potential values. Here, data trials were labeled as artifactual if the absolute value of any data point in the trial exceeded a fixed threshold.

2) Linear trends: Marked linear trends at one electrode typically indicate transient recording-induced current drifts. To detect such events, we measured the goodness of fit of EEG activity to an oblique straight line within a sliding time window. We then either marked or not the data trial depending on the minimum slope of this straight line and its goodness to fit (in terms of r^2).

3) Data Improbability: Most artifacts have “unusual” time courses, e.g., they appear as transient, ‘odd’, or unexpected events, and may be so identified by the outlying values of their statistics relative to normal brain activity. We tested the use of the joint-probability of the observed distribution of data values and the kurtosis of the data value distribution for detecting such artifacts. The joint probability was computed for every data trial at each electrode or independent component.

4) Kurtosis: We used a second measure to detect unusually ‘peaked’ distributions of potential values the kurtosis (K) of the activity values in each trial:

$$K = m_4 - 3m_2^2 \quad (1)$$

$$M_n = E\{(x - m_1)^n\} \quad (2)$$

Where m_n is the n-order central moment of the variable, is the mean and E an expectation function (here, the average). If all activity values are similar, or the values alternate between two or more extremes, the kurtosis will be highly negative. Again, this type of activity is not typical of brain EEG signals. Strong negative kurtosis values usually reflect AC (alternating current) or DC (direct current) artifacts, for example those induced by screen currents, strong induced line noise from electrical machinery, lighting fixtures, or loose electrode contacts. If the kurtosis is highly positive, the activity distribution is highly peaked (usually around zero) with infrequent appearance of extreme values, and the identified data is likely to contain an artifact. Eye blink artifacts, as for example extracted from scalp EEG data by ICA, also have relatively high kurtosis.

5) Spectral pattern: Finally, some EEG artifacts have specific activity and scalp topographies that are more easily identifiable in the frequency domain. For instance, temporal muscle

activations typically induce relatively strong 20-60 Hz activity at temporal electrodes, while saccadic eye blinks produce unusually strong (1-3 Hz) low frequency activity at frontal electrodes. Software routines for performing the artifact detection methods described above are available within the EEGLAB toolbox [8]. For each trial we divided the trials to six epochs and do ICA for them. Then employed five methods described above for rejecting artifacts and mark the illegal epoch, if the percent of the unmarked epochs in each trial less than 30% that trial mark as a corrupt trial and delete from the training or testing set.

V. FEATURE EXTRACTION

For features extraction from the raw EEG data many methods such as time domain, frequency domain, and time–frequency domain are used. Since the EEG is non-stationary in general [9], it is most appropriate to use time–frequency domain methods like wavelet transform (WT) as a mean for feature extraction. The WT provides a more flexible way of time–frequency representation of a signal by allowing the use of variable sized windows. In WT long time windows are used to get a finer low-frequency resolution and short time windows are used to get high-frequency information. Thus, WT gives precise frequency information at low frequencies and precise time information at high frequencies. This makes the WT suitable for the analysis of irregular data patterns, such as impulses occurring at various time instances. The EEG recordings were decomposed into various frequency bands through fourth-level wavelet packet decomposition (WPD). The decomposition filters are usually constructed from the daubechies wavelets, when the data has discontinuities. In this research, based on the analysis of the data, daubechies wavelet was used in the decomposition. The power spectrum, variance and mean of the signal (each channel) are extracted as features. So the feature set for each subject in each trial consisted of 3*number of channels. As a result, the feature matrix was 384 374 359 353 266*18 and 200*21 for subject A and B respectively. Finally, the feature matrix is normalized. Figure 1. SVM classification with a hyperplane that maximizes the separating margin between the two classes (indicated by data points marked by “●”s and “○”s). Support vectors are elements of the training set that lie on the boundary hyperplanes of the two classes.

VI. CLASSIFICATION APPROCHES

A. Neural Networks An artificial neural network (ANN) is an interconnected group of artificial neurons simulating the thinking process of human brain. One can consider an ANN as a “magical” black box trained to achieve expected intelligent process, against the input and output information stream. ANN are useful in application areas such as pattern recognition, classification etc.

1) Multilayered Perceptron Neural Networks: The decision making process of the ANN is holistic, based on the features of input patterns, and is suitable for classification of biomedical data. Typically, multilayer feed forward neural networks can be trained as non-linear classifiers using the generalized backpropagation (BP) algorithm. Our network has one hidden layer with five neurons and output layer with one neuron. We use generalized BP algorithm with momentum for training procedure. Momentum is a standard training technique which is used to speed up convergence and maintain generalization performance [10]. For hidden and output layers, we used bipolar and unipolar sigmoid functions respectively as decision function on the other hand we normalized weights and inputs. With these methods we achieved a NN classifier that is the

most suitable classifier for the task at hand. We determined the most effective set as well as the optimum vector length for high accuracy classification. This NN classifier was trained and tested by using the feature sets described above. By means of minimizing error, we optimized the number of neurons in hidden layer to five. Weights and sigmoid function slope were trained at the next step. With 500 epochs and learning rate equal to 0.05, we achieved classification accuracy equal to 88.75% and 80.87% for subject A and B respectively.

2) Probabilistic Neural Network: The probabilistic approach to neural networks has been developed in the framework of statistical pattern recognition. Probabilistic neural network (PNN) is derived from radial basis function (RBF) network which is an ANN using RBF. RBF is a bell shape function that scales the variable nonlinearly. PNN is adopted for it has many advantages [10]. Its training speed is many times faster than a BP network. PNN can approach a Bayes optimal result under certain easily met conditions. Additionally, it is robust to noise examples. We choose it also for its simple structure and training manner. The most important advantage of PNN is that training is easy and instantaneous. Weights are not “trained” but assigned. Existing weights will never be alternated but only new vectors are inserted into weight matrices when training. So it can be used in real-time. Since the training and running procedure can be implemented by matrix manipulation, the speed of PNN is very fast.

B. Support Vector Machine The SVM is a relatively new classification technique developed by Vapnik [12] which has shown to perform strongly in a number of real-world problems, including BCI. The invention of SVM was driven by underlying statistical learning theory, i.e., following the principle of structural risk minimization that is rooted in VC dimension theory, which makes its derivation even more profound. The SVMs have been a topic of extensive research with wide applications in machine learning and engineering.

Figure 3: SVM classification with a hyperplane that maximizes the separating margin between the two classes (indicated by data points marked by “▲”s and “■”s). Support vectors are elements of the training set that lie on the boundary hyperplanes of the two classes.

The output of a binary SVM classifier can be computed by the following expression:

$$y = \text{sgn} \left(\sum_{i=1}^N \alpha_i y_i k(x_i, x) + b \right) \quad (3)$$

Where $\{x_i, y_i\}_{i=1}^N$ are training samples with input vectors $x_i \in \mathbb{R}^d$ and class labels $y_i = \{-1, 1\}$, $\alpha > 0$, are Lagrangian

multipliers obtained by solving a quadratic optimization problem, b is the bias, and $k(x_i, x_j)$ is called kernel function in SVM.

CONCLUSION

After administration of caffeine, total power in the quantitatively analyzed EEG was significantly reduced at frontal (Fz, F3, F4), central (Cz, C3, C4), temporal (T6), parietal (P3, P4) and occipital (O1, O2) electrode positions when the subjects kept their eyes open ($p < 0.05$). A trend in the same direction was seen with eyes closed in frontal (Fz, F3, F4, F7), central (Cz, C3, C4), temporal (T3, T4, T6), parietal (P3, P4, Pz) and occipital leads (O2), although statistical significance was not reached ($p \geq 0.05$). Caffeine significantly reduced absolute power in the slow and fast alpha (alpha1 and alpha2) as well as the slow beta (beta1) frequency ranges at various electrode positions under the eyes open condition. Alpha power was not significantly affected, whereas beta power was reduced when the subjects kept their eyes closed. Theta and delta activities were diminished in a few leads under both conditions. However, the reduction of alpha power was accentuated in frontal and occipital regions of both hemispheres.

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